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ABSTRACT

The processing of bio-based materials, such as livestock manure, municipal or industrial bio-waste and sewage sludge, facilitates the return of nutrients and organic matter to agriculture. However, processing technologies can also generate emissions such as methane, ammonia or nitrous oxide. The emission potential can affect the sustainability of the technologies and challenge their applicability.

This report examines the dynamics of greenhouse gas (GHG) and nutrient emissions from three different organic waste treatment processes: anaerobic digestion, pyrolysis and composting. Anaerobic digestion, a biological process, produces biogas and digestate, which can emit methane, nitrous oxide and ammonia during the process chain. Carbonisation technologies, such as pyrolysis as a thermal decomposition process, produce biochar and syngas, which can result in GHG emissions. Composting, a natural decomposition process, releases carbon dioxide, ammonia and nitrous oxide during the breakdown of organic matter. Understanding the emission profiles of these processes is crucial for the sustainable production of external organic matter (EOM). This report contributes to the ongoing discourse on climate change mitigation by assessing the environmental impacts of anaerobic digestion, pyrolysis and composting.

This report focuses on the greenhouse gas and nutrient emission risks of anaerobic digestion, pyrolysis and composting processes. The report discusses the emission risks using both literature and experimental data, and suggests best management practices for the treatment of EOMs.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse gas
CH ₄	Methane
NH ₃	Ammonia
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
TS	Total solids
VS	Volatile solids
N	Nitrogen
P	Phosphorus
C	Carbon
CO	Carbon monoxide
H ₂	Hydrogen

1. Introduction

The processing of bio-based materials, such as livestock manure, municipal or industrial bio-waste and sewage sludge, can facilitate the return of both nutrients and organic matter to agriculture. In addition, processing technologies such as anaerobic digestion and the production of biochar through carbonisation technologies have been recognised as environmentally sustainable methods of using e.g., waste materials (Khan et al., 2021; Subbarao et al., 2023). Many studies on the life cycle analysis of anaerobic digestion show, for example, that the climate impact of the digestion process is lower compared to reference treatment methods, e.g., incineration (Mayer et al., 2021). The benefits arise from the production of renewable energy and the avoidance of mineral fertiliser and fossil fuel use. A further benefit may be the production of more stable carbon, which in the long term will support carbon sequestration in soils (Matušík et al., 2020).

However, the processing technologies and practices associated with processing do not necessarily always have only beneficial climate or other types of environmental impacts. For example, there is a risk of methane emissions from anaerobic digestion plants, e.g., from leaks in reactor structures or from digestate storage. Similarly, carbonisation processes can pose an emissions risk due to inefficient operation. Composting is a process, which naturally produced greenhouse gases during the breakdown of organic matter. In addition, nutrient emissions and the risk of eutrophication are always present when nutrient-containing fertiliser products are applied. Biological processes, such as anaerobic digestion and composting, generate CO₂, which are not considered as greenhouse gas (GHG) contributing to global warming. This is because the carbon has a biogenic origin, i.e., this carbon has been previously fixed biologically.

The aim of this report is to focus on the GHG and nutrient emission risks of anaerobic digestion and carbonization processes, based on literature and experimental data generated in the EOM4SOIL project.

2. Anaerobic digestion

Anaerobic digestion involves the microbial degradation of organic matter under anaerobic conditions to produce biogas, a mixture of CO₂ and CH₄. The undegraded organic matter, the digestate, can be used either as a fertiliser or as a soil conditioner. The entire anaerobic digestion process chain consists of several process stages, such as raw material storage, biogas and digestate treatment and storage, and the use of digestate as a fertiliser on fields (Figure 1). When assessing the benefits and potential emission risks throughout anaerobic digestion, it is important to consider the whole process chain.

The risk emissions from the anaerobic digestion chain are greenhouse gases such as methane and nitrous oxide. In addition, gaseous ammonia emissions may occur. Along with the gaseous emission sources, there is also a risk of nutrient emissions in the form of e.g., leaching. Gaseous emissions can occur throughout the production chain (Figure 1), with methane emission risks associated with leaks in process equipment and gas lines, as well as degradation and emission risks from the storage phase. In addition, ammonia can be generated during the storage, digestate treatment and application phases. Nitrous oxide emissions are associated with soil processes following digestate application. Carbon dioxide is also produced along with other gaseous emissions, but these are not discussed in this report. Nutrient emissions in the form of leaching can occur after digestate application.

The GHG and nutrient emissions in this report are assessed on the basis of a brief literature review and calculations based on the pilot-scale digestion experiment.

Figure 1. Anaerobic digestion chain and its greenhouse gas and nutrient emission risks. Modified from (Luostarinen et al., 2023).

2.1 Literature survey on GHG and nutrient emissions

GHG emissions from anaerobic digestion have mainly been reported from wet digestion technologies, and only individual measurement results from different dry digesters have been reported (Liebetrau et al., 2013). In the scientific literature, methane emissions are often reported in terms of 'percentage of methane produced', which refers to the proportion of the measured emission out of the amount of methane in the collected biogas. However, each reported study is individual, reporting results from different digesters and using different measurement methods. It is therefore difficult to compare the reported results. Below, there are brief descriptions of each phase of the anaerobic digestion chain where emissions occur. In addition, Table 1 summarises emission results from the literature.

Emissions from the anaerobic digestion process can occur during raw material handling (feeding and mixing units) or from leaks in the reactor, gas lines and membranes or pressure relief valves. In addition, reactor maintenance can also cause emissions, for example when gas lines need to be opened. These emissions consist of methane that has been produced either in the reactor or during raw material storage. Measures to reduce these emissions are closely linked to good maintenance practices.

During biogas processing, emissions can occur either as losses or leaks from the CHP unit or the methane upgrading unit. For CHP units, emissions can be mitigated through flue gas treatment and equipment maintenance. For methane upgrading, the technologies have different emission

potentials, with chemical scrubbers and membrane technologies being investigated for lower emissions (Luostarinen et al., 2023).

Digestate processing can also cause emissions, so there is little reported data on this topic (Luostarinen et al., 2023). Digestate separation, e.g., with a screw press or centrifuge, can cause methane emissions as some of the gas still bound in the digestate is released. However, the treatment time is often short. In addition, thermal digestate treatment technologies can lead to NH_3 emissions if ammonium in the digestate is volatilised. Volatilisation is highly dependent on pH and temperature, and pH can be used to control volatilisation. From 50 to almost 100% of the soluble nitrogen in the treatable material can be volatilised during drying, depending on drying conditions and material characteristics. In addition, technologies are available to remove NH_3 from the drying gas, e.g., ammonia scrubbers.

Digestate storage emissions are often recognised as the main source of emissions within anaerobic digestion. During storage, all three forms of gaseous emissions, CH_4 , N_2O and NH_3 , are formed due to the continued degradation of the digestate in the storage, of which methane is the most potent. Emissions from the storage depend on the temperature, structure (covered or open), digestate characteristics (e.g., pH) and storage time. In particular, NH_3 emissions are related to temperature and pH. The amount of emissions released during storage is highly dependent on the anaerobic digestion process, in particular its performance and the retention time applied in the reactor. If the digestion process has been run with a short retention time, it is likely that the degradation has not been effective enough and that the digestate still contains degradable organic matter. This residual organic matter will then decompose during storage of the digestate and cause emissions. If the anaerobic digestion process is well managed and operated (i.e., appropriate residence time of the feedstock in the digester), the emission risks will be minimised. In addition, covering the storage units and reducing the temperature of the digestate, e.g., using heat exchangers, can be used to mitigate emission risks.

In addition to the emission risks from the anaerobic digestion process, the use of digestate can result in both gaseous and leaching emissions. These effects depend on the characteristics of the digestate, the soil and the application methods and fertilising rates used. There are known trade-offs between, for example, minimising NH_3 emissions and subsequently increasing N_2O emissions by using different spreading technologies. The emission data from digestate application have not been included in Table 1 because the results are often reported in different units (e.g., % of applied N), which makes it difficult to compare the values.

According to the literature, the measured emissions from the different stages of the process vary, which makes it difficult to estimate the greenhouse gas emission risks of anaerobic digestion.

Table 1. Emissions from different phases of anaerobic digestion chain. Methane emissions are presented as % of the produced methane if not otherwise stated.

		CH ₄ (% produced CH ₄)	N ₂ O	NH ₃	Reference
Digestion process	Feedstock mixing	0.005–0.311			1-2
	Feeding	0.00052–0.16			1-2
	Maintenance	5.04–5.46			1-2
	Pressure release valves	0.04–16.2			3-6
	Leakages	0–4.41			1-2, 7
Biogas utilization	CHP	0.17–3.72			1-2
		3.11–3.23 g/kWh	0,006–0,345 g/kWh		1-2
	Upgrading	0.017–5.34	No emission		5,8-9
Digestate processing	Separation	0.001–0.13	0.0008 kg/h	0.0043 kg/h	1-2, 10
	Drying	No emission		0.08–0.2 g/m ³	11
Digestate storage	Storage	0.00013–12			1-2, 5, 12-15
		0–52 g/m ³ /d	0.004–2.7 g/m ³ /d	0–96.3 g/m ³ /d	12-14, 16-24

1) Liebetrau et al. 2010, 2) Liebetrau et al. 2013, 3) Groth et al. 2015, 4) Reinelt et al. 2016, 5) Reinelt et al. 2017, 6) Reinelt & Liebetrau 2020, 7) Reinelt et al. 2022, 8) Kvist & Aryal 2019, 9) Avfall Sverige 2016, 10) Samuelsson et al. 2018, 11) Awiszus et al. 2018b, 12) Baldé et al. 2016, 13) Balsari et al. 2013, 14) Vergote et al. 2020, 15) Hrad et al. 2015, 16) Baral et al. 2018, 17) Gioelli et al. 2011, 18) Maldaner et al. 2018, 19) Perazzolo et al. 2015, 20) Rodhe et al. 2015, 21) Baldé et al. 2018, 22) Holly et al. 2017, 23) Zilio et al. 2020, 24) Amon et al. 2006

It should also be noted that although anaerobic digestion is associated with a risk of emissions and there are studies showing relatively high emission potentials, emission management is closely linked to the economic performance of digestion plants. The higher the emissions from the plant (either as CH₄ or as NH₃ and N₂O), the lower the amount of CH₄ captured and the nutrient quality of the digestate. Thus, emission control benefits both the environment and the plant operator. Emission abatement may also entail costs, such as increased reactor capacity (to ensure adequate retention time) and covered storage.

In Finland, the sustainability of biogas production has been addressed in the government programme and further implemented in a research project. The results of the project are available in (Luostarinen et al., 2023).

2.2 Emission potential based on a pilot experiment

A pilot-scale experiment was conducted in a mesophilic (37 °C) batch-type leach-bed process to study the effect of co-digestion of cow manure and straw on the mass, carbon and nitrogen balances. The detailed description of the study is included in the manuscript by Tampio et al. (2024), which has been submitted to a journal as EOM4SOIL's D2.1. The aim of the balance calculations was to estimate the potential of batch-type solid anaerobic digestion for GHG and nutrient emissions.

2.2.1 Methods

The raw materials used were solid dairy manure and winter wheat straw (Table 2). Both materials were obtained from Luke's barn in Jokioinen, Finland. The experiment consisted of parallel reactors (referred to as R1 and R2) filled with manure and straw in multiple layers, with straw as the bottom and top layer. The straw was added in such a way that it made up 15.7% of the total feed mass in the reactors. This ratio was chosen because it corresponded to 40% of the total carbon of the straw in the feedstock mixture, which showed the best methane production performance in previous laboratory scale tests.

Percolate liquid was used as the microbial inoculum in the reactors and was obtained from a full-scale biogas plant. The percolate liquid was circulated through the solid substrate batch. The recirculation was set to circulate 10 litres of liquid every 48 hours during the start-up phase of the process. Later, the recirculation was intensified to recirculate 10 L every 24, 12, 6, 4 and 2 hours, depending on the stage of the digestion process. On day 65 of the experiment, due to an equipment malfunction, the circulation in R2 was switched to less frequent feeding, circulating 10 L every 24 hours with breaks over the weekends. Tap water, a total of 207 L in R1 and 229 L in R2, was added to the percolation liquid tanks to maintain a constant volume of liquid in the tanks. Water was added because the feed materials absorbed relatively large amounts of water.

During the reactor runs, temperature, pH, biogas volume and methane content were measured daily. At the end of the experiment, the reactors were emptied of the liquid contained in the biomass. Both digestate and percolate liquid were sampled and analysed (Table 2). The experiment lasted 139 days.

Mass, carbon and nitrogen balances were calculated based on the quality and quantity of biogas produced and the characteristics of the feedstock, inoculum, digestate and percolate liquid. The amount of water added during the reactor runs was taken into account when calculating the mass balance. The balances are presented as percentages of R1 and R2 reactors. In the absence of analytical data, percolate C was assumed to be 55% of VS and percolate N was assumed to be the same as in the post-process percolate. No gaseous emissions were assumed to occur (e.g. as leakage from reactor or gas lines).

Figure 2. a) Schematics of the reactor, b) and c) filling and packing the reactor with straw and manure, d) digestate after 139 of digestion.

Photos by Niina Honkala.

Table 2. Feedstock, digestate and percolate characteristics. Empty cells refer to no analytical data available.

		Feedstocks		Digestates		Percolate liquids	
		CM	WS	R1	R2	R1	R2
TS	%	23.9	91.4	12.5	12.9	1.1	1.1
VS	%TS	91.3	93.2	83.5	85.4	49.1	41.7
C	%TS	48.0	46.3	46.0	46.1		
H	%TS	5.9	6.2	4.8	5.3		
N	%TS	2.2	0.6	2.0	2.0		
S	%TS	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.3		
O	%TS	34.9	39.9	30.3	31.8		
ash	%TS	8.7	6.9	16.5	14.6		
N Kjeldahl	g/kg FM			3.0	2.8		
NH4-N	g/kg FM	5.5	0.4	1	0.8	0.4	0.4
P	g/kg FM	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.3		
K	g/kg FM	3.7	14.7	4.8	5.0		

From fresh feedstocks, digestate and percolate samples the total solids (TS) and the volatile solids (VS) were analysed according to SFS 3008 (Finnish Standard Association, Helsinki, 1990). Total nitrogen (N Kjeldahl) and soluble ammonium N (NH₄-N) were analysed by the Kjeldahl method using FOSS Kjeltec 8400 (FOSS, Denmark). From dried samples, the content of C, hydrogen (H), N, and sulphur (S) was determined using a Leco CHN628 elemental analyser (Leco Corporation, USA), and

oxygen (O) was calculated based on mass balance. The concentrations of P and K were analysed with an ICP-OES (Perkin Elmer Optima 8300) after HNO₃ digestion.

2.2.2 Results and discussion

The mass, carbon and nitrogen balances from the co-digestion experiment were based on the process inputs and outputs and their characteristics during parallel 139-day batch-type reactor runs. The results in Figures 3-6 are presented as percentages of the total inputs to the digestion process. Nitrogen balances are presented as total nitrogen and ammonium nitrogen. A phosphorus balance was not carried out as it was not analysed from all inputs and outputs. In addition, phosphorus is a non-volatilisable compound that was assumed to remain in the process outputs, namely digestate and percolate liquid.

Most of the mass of the input materials (manure, straw, inoculum and added water) was retained in the digestate (46% of the mass of the inputs) and in the percolate (31%) (Figure 3). Only a small fraction of the input mass (3%) was retained in the biogas. There were mass losses totalling 20% of the input mass, probably mainly due to unmeasured water vapour in the biogas. Although the added water contributed the highest mass of inputs to the reactors, the majority of C came from the feedstocks, manure and straw. During the digestion process, the readily degradable fraction of the organic matter is broken down into CO₂ and CH₄, so 25% of the C from the input was captured as biogas. Most of the C (58%) remained in the digestate. Some C losses were also detected in the C balance, but it was not clear whether the losses were due to mere assumptions in the C balance calculations or real losses of C in the form of CH₄ and CO₂, e.g., when opening the reactor after the digestion process.

The total nitrogen balance (Figure 5) was mainly based on the nitrogen in the manure, which was further concentrated in the digestate. However, no total nitrogen losses were detected. During anaerobic digestion, nitrogen is partly mineralised to NH₄-N. Due to the volatile nature of NH₄-N (as NH₃), it was expected that the N balance would show N losses. However, N losses were only detected when the NH₄-N balance was calculated (Figure 6). Due to the mineralisation of N, the content of NH₄-N in the digestate and percolate should have increased during digestion, but this effect was not detected. A very high proportion of NH₄-N was lost in the process, 63%. The losses may be high due to the inaccuracy of the analyses as there was no NH₄-N measurement from the inoculum. However, due to the large amount of NH₄-N lost, it is likely that it was volatilised as NH₃ when the reactor was opened and emptied.

Mass balances can give an indication of the emission risks from the anaerobic digestion process itself. In this study, the batch-type solid digestion process was found to have the potential to generate emissions in the form of carbon (CH₄ and CO₂), and NH₄-N losses were also observed. As the process is batch type, where the reactor is opened after the digestion process, there is a potential for gaseous emissions to escape, i.e., biogas still trapped in the reactor contents. At the same time, NH₄-N can also escape in the form of NH₃ if the conditions (pH and temperature) are favourable. More detailed monitoring of biogas reactors would therefore be needed to estimate the potential for greenhouse gas emissions. This would include, for example, more detailed analyses of the individual fractions and the measurement of possible gas emissions as leaks from the process, especially during the emptying phase of the reactor.

Figure 3. Mass balance of the batch-type anaerobic digestion.

Figure 4. Carbon balance of the batch-type anaerobic digestion.

Figure 5. Nitrogen balance of the batch-type anaerobic digestion.

Figure 6. Ammonium nitrogen balance of the batch-type anaerobic digestion.

3. Carbonization processes

Carbonization is a thermochemical process by which organic, mostly biogenic raw material is converted into solid residues with increasing content of carbon; usually this is achieved by pyrolysis in an inert atmosphere. In addition to the solid products, the process may yield also liquid and gaseous by-products, depending on the process conditions pressure, temperature, residence time and oxygen supply. The higher the oxygen supply, the more gaseous products are produced until – with complete oxidation of the biomass – combustion results. The products can either be recycled (e.g., biochar or bio-oils), but can also be used for energy recovery (e.g., syngas).

During slow pyrolysis (residence times from minutes to hours, temperatures 350-750 °C, slow heating rates) about 35 % of input dry matter is converted to solid residues (biochar), about 35 % to gases (syngas) and about 30 % to condensable liquids (Kaltschmitt et al., 2016). Focusing on the fate of carbon during pyrolysis, about half of the carbon in the input material will be conserved in biochar and the other half goes to the volatile fraction of pyrolysis.

3.1 Fate of nutrients during pyrolysis

Most nutrient elements from the feedstock are conserved in biochar. Their concentrations are increasing similar to the carbon concentration. The elements sulphur and nitrogen are important exceptions. At pyrolysis temperature of 300 to 500 °C, about 50 % of sulphur may be released but not much more at higher temperatures (Lang et al., 2005). Nitrogen release starts at about 400 °C, and typical pyrolysis temperatures of 500-650 °C cause the loss of about half of the input material nitrogen. The remaining nitrogen in biochar has very slow release rates and low bioavailability as it is mostly bound in heterocyclic compounds (Baser et al., 2021).

Phosphorus is more stable, release starts only at temperatures above 700 °C which are usually beyond the intended process temperatures of pyrolysis (Sun et al., 2016). The stability of phosphorus and potassium during pyrolysis are the basis for the potential of slow nutrient release after biochar incorporation into soil. Kloss et al. (2014) have shown that P and K from biochar contribute significantly to the P and K supply of crop plants, especially when the biochar was straw-based (biochars made from leafy materials usually have higher nutrient concentrations than wood-based biochars). Bioavailabilities of feedstock-derived P and K in biochar are higher than N bioavailability. Bio-oil is the condensable fraction of the volatile pyrolysis products and is composed of long-chain hydrocarbons without significant nutrient fractions. Therefore, bio-oil only plays a role as liquid energy carrier (substitute for crude-oil based liquid fuels) or as base material for fine chemicals or pharmaceuticals.

3.2 Greenhouse gas emissions during pyrolysis

The gaseous nitrogen release during pyrolysis may consist of molecular nitrogen and nitrogen oxides. With respect to greenhouse gas potential, N₂O deserves special attention. In all modern pyrolysis units, the post-combustion of syngas is an essential module of the whole facility. The energy release of the post-combustion can be used for heating purposes – partly for direct heating of the reactor tube, partly for local heat exchange systems or feedstock drying. The exhaust gases of the post-combustion are strictly regulated by the authorities to avoid a violation of national emission regulations. This combustion causes an N₂O-decomposition rate of up to 99 % (Hu et al., 2011) so the greenhouse gas potential of the combusted syngas will be much lower than of primary syngas.

As energy carrier, syngas is considered as clean fuel with great potential value for contributing to carbon neutrality (Zhuang et al., 2022). Syngas as the gaseous fraction of pyrolysis products may contain methane up to a few %, alongside with the other syngas components CO, H₂, and CO₂. However, the post-combustion stage of a pyrolysis reactor completely oxidizes the methane to CO and CO₂, thereby decreasing the GHG potential of methane by a factor of 27. By the way, methane pyrolysis is considered as an interesting bridge technology on the pathway to a hydrogen economy (Sánchez-Bastardo et al., 2021).

In the calculation of carbon credits based on biochar, a margin of safety of 10% of all greenhouse gas emissions is considered when calculating the carbon sink potential of biochar production (EBC, 2020). Most biochars are characterized by carbon concentrations of 70-80 % if they are produced from plant materials. Generally, the calculation of biochar-based carbon sinks for compliance with trading platforms consider the emissions from the production of agricultural or forest biomass (fertilization, diesel fuel) as well as the methane emissions during the storage of biomass before pyrolysis, the transport of the biomass and, after pyrolysis, of the produced biochar, the pyrolysis process itself and the potential post-treatment of biochar.

3.3 Hydrothermal carbonization

Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC), also known as aqueous charring, is a process in which biochar is produced from organic material under temperatures of 180 to 250°C, autogenous pressure and in the presence of water. At higher temperatures and pressures, hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL, 250-400°C, 30-250 bar, main products: aqueous and oily phase, also known as bio-crude oil). A further increase is referred to as hydrothermal gasification (HTG, > 350°C, > 250 bar, main product: synthesis gas (=syngas)). Hydrothermal carbonization is preferred for biomass with a high water content (>50 %; Quicker and Weber, 2016). In the relevant literature, the term hydrochar has become firmly established for biochar produced by HTC.

Depending on the input material and the process conditions, 50-80% of the input mass is found in the solid product, 5-20% in the aqueous phase and 2-5% in the gas phase. The product hydrochar is more hydrophobic than the feedstock and the dewatering is less energy-intensive than the dewatering of the biomass. Due to the increased carbon content, the calorific value of hydrochar increases. The distribution of nutrients between the solid, liquid and gaseous phases can be adjusted via the process conditions (pressure, temperature, residence time, heating rate, pH, ...). The process conditions can be adjusted in such a way that nutrients such as phosphorus are largely found in the process water. By means of precipitation processes (e.g., struvite process), phosphorus can then be removed from the process water and used as fertilizer.

As hydrochar is usually produced by a batchwise HTC process, both the gases and the residual liquid can be collected and treated as necessary to avoid undesired greenhouse gas emissions. Hydrochar is characterized by much lower mean residence time in soil than pyrolytic biochar (decades vs. centuries; Kammann et al., 2012).

3.4 Thermochemical biomass gasification

Thermochemical gasification is the process of converting dry, solid biomass into a hydrogen-containing gas and charcoal in the absence of oxygen and at high temperatures (up to 1100 °C). The complex conversion process consists of four main process steps: drying, pyrolysis, partial oxidation and gasification (reduction). Depending on the technology, the individual process steps can be

carried out in a single reactor or, in staged processes, carried out separately in separate reactors (Kaltschmitt et al., 2016). The difference between gasification and combustion is the lack of oxygen during the gasification step. The required oxygen for partial oxidation can be supplied in the form of air or pure oxygen, as well as in the form of water vapor and even carbon dioxide.

Although most gasification processes have been developed for energy production with a very low yield of solid residues, the process can be shifted into the direction of biochar production by appropriate control of the process parameters. Combined gasification-pyrolysis plants may yield up to 10 % of high quality biochar in spite of the focus on thermal energy provision for district heating systems. Gasification char is more relevant as technical carbon and not as carrier of nutrients from the input materials. With respect to greenhouse gas emissions, similar principles as described for pyrolysis chars are valid. The syngas produced by gasification consists mainly of hydrogen and carbon monoxide that can be used for thermal energy or for chemical synthesis.

4. Composting

Composting is an aerobic microbial degradation process that produces N_2O , CH_4 and NH_3 as well as CO_2 and H_2O . The biological phase of the composting process is often considered to be the main source of GHG emissions within the processing chain, which often includes feedstock acquisition, material storage and application. However, the results are highly dependent on the amount of emissions assumed in the analysis (Saer et al., 2013). For example, not all LCA studies include emissions (Oviedo-Ocaña et al., 2023).

Methane emissions from composting are associated with the formation of anaerobic conditions in the thermophilic phase of the process, where high temperatures reduce the solubility of oxygen. During the composting process, CH_4 can also be reduced by oxidative methanotrophic microbes. Nitrous oxide is produced in small amounts but is formed throughout the composting process where nitrification and denitrification processes occur due to the presence of both oxic and anoxic conditions. In addition to CH_4 and N_2O , some studies have reported the formation of CO during the composting process. NH_4 is formed during the mineralisation of N, which is also dependent on pH and temperature. Especially from the point of view of nutrient recycling, the avoidance of NH_3 and N_2O emissions benefits the use of compost as a fertiliser, as more nitrogen can be recovered with the compost product.

Although GHG emissions are a natural part of the process, there are methods to reduce emissions. There are several composting technologies, which also have an effect on gaseous emissions, depending for example on the aeration rate and whether the system is open or closed. In particular, CH_4 emissions can be minimised with sufficient aeration to prevent anaerobic conditions. However, there may be trade-offs between different emissions, e.g., if aeration potentially reduces CH_4 but increases NH_3 emissions. Another example is biofiltering to remove NH_3 , which has been reviewed to increase N_2O production (Sánchez et al., 2015).

In addition, the characteristics of the compostable material play an important role in the generation of emissions. In particular, the C/N ratio and the N content of the material affect NH_3 and N_2O emissions (Sánchez et al., 2015). Additives can also be used to reduce emissions. For example, biochar has been used to reduce CH_4 and NH_3 emissions from compost (Yin et al., 2021).

The emission potential of composting has been studied in both laboratory and full-scale composting facilities. Recently, many reviews (Sánchez et al., 2015; Yasmin et al., 2022) and meta-analyses (Ba et

al., 2020) have been published on GHG and NH₃ emissions from composting processes. Table 3 summarises emission factors from a few studies focusing on the composting of municipal and industrial waste with different technologies. The table shows the large variability of emissions from different composting applications.

Table 3. Emissions from composting of municipal and industrial waste materials.

Material	Technology	CH ₄ kg/t waste	N ₂ O kg/t waste	NH ₃ kg/t waste	Reference
Solid waste		0.03–8	0.06–0.6		IPCC, 2006
OFMSW	Windrow, turned windrow	0.34–4.37	0.035– 0.251		Colón et al., 2012
OFMSW	Open composting	0.02–1.8	0.0075– 0.252		Boldrin et al., 2009
Poultry slaughtering wastes and manure	Closed reactor, different aeration rates	0.0052–0.012	0.005– 0.006	1.2–2.4	Zhu et al., 2014
Different waste materials	Windrow	0.021–11.9	0.0003– 0.252	0.025–1.3	Review by Saer et al., 2013
Manure	Windrow	0.79–1.7			Vergara and Silver, 2019
Food waste	Not available	0.17–0.19	0.1–0.13		Jeong et al., 2019

OFMSW= organic fraction of municipal solid waste

5. Best practises in processing of EOMs

The best practices for reducing and managing treatment with anaerobic digestion, carbonisation and composting are summarised in Table 3. Although the three technologies examined have different characteristics, similar recommendations can be made.

Table 4. Best practises in processing of EOMs.

Process phase	Actions
Equipment maintenance	Practices to prevent leaks and unintentional gas emissions from the system
Storage and handling of raw materials and end products	Preventing emissions from material degradation during the storage phase For example, closed or covered storage systems are recommended
Process operation	Utilization of best available technologies to prevent emissions from the process For example, appropriate retention time in anaerobic digestion and well-managed composting system with optimal aeration and feed C/N ratio Post-combustion to avoid flue gas emissions (when using e.g. syngas or biogas)
Use of nutrient recovery technologies	Nutrient recovery from process by-products, rejects and gaseous phases For example, use of ammonia scrubbers to capture NH ₃ from composting air
End product application	Timely fertilisation according to crop nutrient requirements Use of application methods that reduce NH ₃ emissions (e.g. mulching)
Consideration of carbon stability credits	Especially applicable to biochar

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